

Analysis of the teleworking adoption in the post-pandemic period

My name is Filipe Costa and I'm an MSc student in Informatic Engineering at the University of Minho. As part of my master's thesis, I'm developing an analysis of the remote working adoption among Portuguese software development teams.

With this questionnaire, I intend to collect data that will allow me to understand:

- which is the preferred work regimen among the members of the software development teams;
- the motivations behind such choices;
- how much flexibility is offered by employers;
- analyse how to make the coexistence between remote and on-site work more productive;
- allow for greater flexibility for workers without prejudice to teams and employers.

The questionnaire is completely anonymous and only intended for members of software development teams, whether they work remotely or on-office. It is composed of a maximum of 25 questions (only two of which are open-ended ones) and should take no more than 7 minutes.

Should you have any questions or wish to receive the dissertation, please feel welcome to contact me, at the following email address: pg47179@alunos.uminho.pt

Thank you in advance for your collaboration.

* Indicates required question

1. This study does not include any form of financial compensation, nor is it financed by any external entity, and participation in it is entirely voluntary. *

Full confidentiality of the collected data will be ensured, and it will only be used for academic purposes.

Mark only one oval.

I declare that I am aware that the data I have provided is confidential and anonymous, and I authorize its use for academic purposes.

Demographic data

2. 1) What is your age group? *

Mark only one oval.

18-25 years

26-35 years

36-50 years

51-65 years

65+ years

3. 2) What is your gender? *

Mark only one oval.

Female

Male

I prefer not to say

Other: _____

4. 3) Where were you born *

Mark only one oval.

- Portugal
- Brazil
- Angola
- Cabo Verde
- Guinea-Bissau
- Mozambique
- São Tomé and Príncipe
- Afghanistan
- Albania
- Algeria
- American Samoa
- Andorra
- Antigua and Barbuda
- Argentina
- Armenia
- Aruba
- Australia
- Austria
- Azerbaijan
- Bahamas, The
- Bahrain
- Bangladesh
- Barbados
- Belarus
- Belgium
- Belize
- Benin
- Bermuda
- Bhutan
- Bolivia
- Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Botswana

- British Virgin Islands
- Brunei Darussalam
- Bulgaria
- Burkina Faso
- Burundi
- Cambodia
- Cameroon
- Canada
- Cayman Islands
- Central African Republic
- Chad
- Channel Islands
- Chile
- China
- Colombia
- Comoros
- Congo, Dem. Rep.
- Congo, Rep.
- Costa Rica
- Cote d'Ivoire
- Croatia
- Cuba
- Curacao
- Cyprus
- Czechia
- Denmark
- Djibouti
- Dominica
- Dominican Republic
- Ecuador
- Egypt, Arab Rep.
- El Salvador
- Equatorial Guinea
- Eritrea
- Estonia

- Eswatini
- Ethiopia
- Faroe Islands
- Fiji
- Finland
- France
- French Polynesia
- Gabon
- Gambia, The
- Georgia
- Germany
- Ghana
- Gibraltar
- Greece
- Greenland
- Grenada
- Guam
- Guatemala
- Guinea
- Guyana
- Haiti
- Honduras
- Hong Kong SAR, China
- Hungary
- Iceland
- India
- Indonesia
- Iran, Islamic Rep.
- Iraq
- Ireland
- Isle of Man
- Israel
- Italy
- Jamaica
- Japan

- Jordan
- Kazakhstan
- Kenya
- Kiribati
- Korea, Dem. People's Rep.
- Korea, Rep.
- Kosovo
- Kuwait
- Kyrgyz Republic
- Lao PDR
- Latvia
- Lebanon
- Lesotho
- Liberia
- Libya
- Liechtenstein
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Macao SAR, China
- Madagascar
- Malawi
- Malaysia
- Maldives
- Mali
- Malta
- Marshall Islands
- Mauritania
- Mauritius
- Mexico
- Micronesia, Fed. Sts.
- Moldova
- Monaco
- Mongolia
- Montenegro
- Morocco

- Myanmar
- Namibia
- Nauru
- Nepal
- Netherlands
- New Caledonia
- New Zealand
- Nicaragua
- Niger
- Nigeria
- North Macedonia
- Northern Mariana Islands
- Norway
- Oman
- Pakistan
- Palau
- Panama
- Papua New Guinea
- Paraguay
- Peru
- Philippines
- Poland
- Puerto Rico
- Qatar
- Romania
- Russian Federation
- Rwanda
- Samoa
- San Marino
- Saudi Arabia
- Senegal
- Serbia
- Seychelles
- Sierra Leone
- Singapore

- Sint Maarten (Dutch part)
- Slovak Republic
- Slovenia
- Solomon Islands
- Somalia
- South Africa
- South Sudan
- Spain
- Sri Lanka
- St. Kitts and Nevis
- St. Lucia
- St. Martin (French part)
- St. Vincent and the Grenadines
- Sudan
- Suriname
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- Syrian Arab Republic
- Tajikistan
- Tanzania
- Thailand
- Timor-Leste
- Togo
- Tonga
- Trinidad and Tobago
- Tunisia
- Turkiye
- Turkmenistan
- Turks and Caicos Islands
- Tuvalu
- Uganda
- Ukraine
- United Arab Emirates
- United Kingdom
- United States

- Uruguay
- Uzbekistan
- Vanuatu
- Venezuela, RB
- Vietnam
- Virgin Islands (U.S.)
- West Bank and Gaza
- Yemen, Rep.
- Zambia
- Zimbabwe

5. 4) Are you part of a professional software development team? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

Academic and Professional Data

6. 5) What is your academic background? *

Mark only one oval.

- High school
- Bachelor's degree
- Masters
- PhD
- Other: _____

7. 6) How many years of experience do you have in the software development industry? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than a year
- 1-2 years
- 2-5 years
- 5-10 years
- 10-20 years
- 20+ years

8. 7) What is your job position at the company? *

Mark only one oval.

- Back-End Developer
- Front-End Developer
- Mobile Developer
- Data Scientist
- Product Designer
- Product Manager
- Full-Stack Developer
- Security Engineer
- Project Manager
- DevOps Engineer
- System Administrator
- Graphics Developer
- Test Engineer
- Performance Engineer
- Database Administrator
- Scrum Master
- Business Analyst
- UI/UX Designer
- Machine Learning Engineer
- Other: _____

9. 8) What is the name of the company you currently work for? *

In this question, **the information collected will not be disclosed** and will only be used to identify possible biased results

Work arrangements

10. 9) In which of the following arrangements are you currently working? *

Mark only one oval.

Fully on-site *Skip to question 23*

Hybrid *Skip to question 14*

Fully remote *Skip to question 18*

11. 10) Select all arrangements in which you worked in the pre-pandemic period *
as part of software development teams

Pre-pandemic refers to the time period **before March 2020**

Tick all that apply.

Fully on-office

Hybrid

Fully remote

I had never worked in software development before the COVID-19 pandemic

12. 11) Select all arrangements in which you worked in the post-pandemic *
period as part of software development teams.

Post-pandemic refers to the time period **between March 2022 and today**

Tick all that apply.

Fully on-office

Hybrid

Fully remote

13. 12) How much flexibility does your employer currently offer with regard to remote working? **(please select all that apply)** *

Tick all that apply.

- Allows full on-office arrangement
- Allows hybrid arrangement
- Allows full remote arrangement

Productivity in hybrid arrangement

14. 13) Do you feel there is any difference between the productivity achieved when working on-office versus remotely? *

Mark only one oval.

- I feel that productivity is substantially higher when working remotely
- I feel that productivity is slightly higher when working remotely
- I feel there is no difference between productivity when working remotely and on-office
- I feel that productivity is slightly higher when I work on-office
- I feel that productivity is substantially higher when I work on-office

15. 14) What strategies do you use to stay productive when working remotely? **(select all that apply)**

Tick all that apply.

- Communicate frequently with my teammates
- Only communicate with my teammates when strictly necessary
- Defining clear boundaries between work and relaxation
- Define work periods with regular short breaks
- Prioritize tasks
- Having a dedicated and organised workspace
- Keep my mobile phone away or turn off notifications
- Dressing similarly to an on-office working day
- Other: _____

16. 15) When working remotely, do you think you have an adequate workspace that allows you to be productive? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, I believe I have a workspace that is fully equipped and adapted to my needs.
- Yes, however I feel that my workspace could be improved
- No, I feel my workspace is inadequate, thus affecting my productivity
- No, in fact, I don't even have a dedicated workspace, thus affecting my productivity

17. 16) On average, how many extra hours per day are you forced to work beyond your working hours? *

Consider only the time period after the end of mandatory remote working (roughly, from March 2022 until today)

Mark only one oval per row.

	0 hours	Less than 1 hour	1-2 hours	2-3 hours	3-4 hours	4+ hours
When working on-office	<input type="radio"/>					
When working remotely	<input type="radio"/>					

Skip to question 27

Productivity in remote arrangement

18. 13) If you have ever worked on-office, do you feel there is any difference between the productivity achieved when working on-office versus remotely? *

Mark only one oval.

- I feel that productivity is substantially higher when working remotely
- I feel that productivity is slightly higher when working remotely
- I feel there is no difference between productivity when working remotely and on-office
- I feel that productivity is slightly higher when I work on-office
- I feel that productivity is substantially higher when I work on-office
- I have never worked on-office, consequently, I cannot compare

19. 14) What strategies do you use to stay productive when working remotely? **(select all that apply)**

Tick all that apply.

- Communicate frequently with my teammates
- Only communicate with my teammates when strictly necessary
- Defining clear boundaries between work and relaxation
- Define work periods with regular short breaks
- Prioritize tasks
- Having a dedicated and organised workspace
- Keep my mobile phone away or turn off notifications
- Dressing similarly to an on-office working day
- Other: _____

20. 15) When working remotely, do you think you have an adequate workspace that allows you to be productive? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, I believe I have a workspace that is fully equipped and adapted to my needs.
- Yes, however I feel that my workspace could be improved
- No, I feel my workspace is inadequate, thus affecting my productivity
- No, in fact, I don't even have a dedicated workspace, thus affecting my productivity

21. 16) On average, how many extra hours per day are you forced to work beyond your working hours? *

Consider only the time period after the end of mandatory remote working (roughly, from March 2022 until today)

Mark only one oval per row.

	0 hours	Less than 1 hour	1-2 hours	2-3 hours	3-4 hours	4+ hours
When working remotely	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

22. 17) Since you work remotely, do you feel that you have the same opportunities to be promoted as your colleagues who work on-office? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- I cannot answer, I am not part of a team with on-office members

Skip to question 27

Productivity in on-office arrangement

23. 13) If you have ever worked remotely, do you feel there is any difference between the productivity achieved when working on-office versus remotely? *

Mark only one oval.

- I feel that productivity is substantially higher when working remotely
- I feel that productivity is slightly higher when working remotely
- I feel there is no difference between productivity when working remotely and on-office
- I feel that productivity is slightly higher when I work on-office
- I feel that productivity is substantially higher when I work on-office
- I have never worked remotely, consequently, I cannot compare

26. 16) Do you feel that team spirit would be strengthened if your whole team worked on-office? *

Mark only one oval.

- I feel that team spirit would be substantially strengthened
- I feel that team spirit would be slightly strengthened
- I feel it would have no impact
- I feel that team spirit would be slightly weakened
- I feel that team spirit would be substantially weakened
- I cannot answer, all my colleagues work on-office too

Skip to question 27

Improvements

Please note that depending on the answer to question 9), it is possible that the numbering does not match that of the last question.

27. 18) Do you feel that the existence of remote workers has any impact on the dynamics and collaboration between team members? *

Mark only one oval.

- I feel that there is a substantial negative impact due to remote working
- I feel there is a slight negative impact due to remote working
- I feel that there is no difference in the dynamics and collaboration of my team due to remote working
- I feel there is a slight positive impact due to remote working
- I feel that there is a substantial positive impact due to remote working
- I can't answer, I've never been part of a team composed of on-office and remote workers (in hybrid mode or not)

28. 19) Do you think that remote workers are well-integrated into team meetings and dynamics? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, I have always felt that they are adequately integrated
- Yes, however at some points I felt they could have been better integrated
- No, I often felt that they are not adequately integrated.
- No, I feel that remote workers are totally out of place with the rest of the team.
- I can't answer, I've never been part of a team composed of on-site and remote workers (in hybrid mode or not)

29. 20) Do you think that your employer should promote more activities or informal conversations to foster team spirit (particularly with those working remotely)? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, it would help me connect with colleagues I don't know outside of work
- Yes, however, I feel there is a healthy team spirit already
- No, I feel that enough activities are already scheduled for this purpose
- No, I feel such activities to be a waste of time

30. 21) Do you think that simple questions that would be answered promptly in on-office mode require, when working remotely, meetings or prolonged waits for answers, thus hindering productivity? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, my productivity is hindered by the difficulties of remote communication
- Communication can be equally effective whether it is done in person or remotely
- No, on the contrary, I feel that communication is more effective when remote
- I cannot answer, I have never been part of a team with remote workers (in hybrid mode or not)

31. 22) Which strategies have your team adopted to improve the adoption of remote working, and what additional suggestions do you have to improve it even further?

(e.g., to address potential challenges related to communication, personal motivation, productivity, team collaboration, leadership...)

Please indicate which measures were already adopted and which are suggestions

32. 23) Which of the following working arrangements do you prefer? (you can choose an arrangement you have never had the opportunity to experience before) *

Mark only one oval.

- Fully on-site *Skip to question 33*
- Hybrid (3 or 4 days on-site) *Skip to question 35*
- Hybrid (1 or 2 days on-site) *Skip to question 35*
- Fully remotely *Skip to question 37*

On-site Arrangement

33. 24) What are the main factors that justify your preference for the fully on-site arrangement? *

34. 25) In a scenario where you were looking for new challenges, and you had in your hands two job offers with similar conditions, one enabling on-office work and the other not, would you give priority to the first one? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, in fact, I would decline any offer prohibiting on-office work
- Yes, however, I could consider the proposal prohibiting on-office work, if it offers better conditions
- No

Hybrid Arrangement

35. 24) What are the main factors that justify your preference for the hybrid arrangement? *

36. 25) In a scenario where you were looking for new challenges, and you had in your hands two job offers with similar conditions, one enabling remote work and the other not, would you give priority to the first one? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, in fact, I would decline any offer prohibiting remote work
- Yes, however, I could consider the proposal prohibiting remote work, if it offers better conditions
- No

Remote Arrangement

37. 24) What are the main factors that justify your preference for the fully remote arrangement? *

38. 25) In a scenario where you were looking for new challenges, and you had in your hands two job offers with similar conditions, one enabling remote work and the other not, would you give priority to the first one? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, in fact, I would decline any offer prohibiting remote work
- Yes, however, I could consider the proposal prohibiting remote work, if it offers better conditions
- No

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